

Effectiveness of the Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU) in its Anti-Criminality Campaign in Bulusan, Sorsogon

JaynorGeroliaGuelas
University of the Cordilleras, Philippines
College of Criminal Justice Education
Graduate School

Abstract:- This topic pertains to the identification of the effectiveness of the Mobile Patrol Unit in Bulusan Sorsogon, including the perception of the people particularly the business-owners based on the programs implemented by the Mobile Patrol Unit. It was previously conducted in the exclusive jurisdiction of the municipality of Bulusan, a fourth-class municipality of the province of Sorsogon, Philippines. The researcher believed that the result of this study could be more beneficial to the said patrol unit in order for them to improve programs and techniques to produce more efficient service to the people. To be able to possibly get the data needed for this study, the researcher used a qualitative research method blended with a descriptive approach. Participants of this study came from the two group of respondents, one from the group of the Philippine National Police (PNP) patrol units (Mobile Patrol Units - MPU) and the other is from the group of the business-owners. Data shows that the Mobile Patrol Unit have their different programs in order to promote the peace and order in the said municipality; their identified programs are: (a)Increased Police Visibility, (b)Positive Attitude, and (c)Multi-Faceted Response. Identified programs are said to have a better effectiveness in as far as the anti-criminality campaign is concern. The low count of crime rate in the said municipality evidenced the said effectiveness of the patrol unit. The greater the program of crime prevention, the greater also the probability to deny the opportunity to commit crime. It also revealed the different positive experiences of the business-owners as to the anti-criminality campaign of the said patrol unit, the identified responses as to the experiences are (a)Community Satisfaction, (b)Good Police Performance, (c)People and Business Security, and (d)Limited Patrol Areas. It evidenced also the effectiveness of the patrol unit of Bulusan municipality. However, the other group of respondents (business-owners) argued that despite of having a good experience, they want to extend the area coverage of conducting patrol by the said unit as it does not reach the far distant barangays in the said municipality. It is exclusively conducted within the entire jurisdiction of the town without significant extension of patrol to the distant areas. Therefore, the researcher concluded that despite of having a better patrol experience of the business owners, the MPU has its own limited area during the times when they are conducting patrol in the municipality of Bulusan, province of Sorsogon.

Keywords:- Effectiveness, Anti-Criminality Campaign, Experiences, Patrol, Philippine National Police, Mobile Patrol Unit, Bulusan, Sorsogon.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

The Patrol is an indispensable service that plays a leading role in the accomplishment of the police purpose. It is the only form of police service that directly attempts to eliminate the opportunity for misconduct (Almoguera, Buyo et. al., 2019). With this, the people, properties and the entire surroundings should be felt secured and free from any dangerous acts from criminals. Here, the researcher will try to picture-out the current situation of Bulusan municipality in relation to the anti-criminality campaign of the Municipal Police Station of the said municipality in order to assess and study the factors that affect to the effectiveness of police presence and its possible solution.

The proliferation of the anti-social behavior even in a rural area dramatically setted-in as in the case of London indicates that for the majority of the travelling public, the forms of anti-social behaviour, which concerns them is more likely to be low-level behaviour, ranging from groups of young people behaving boisterously to people eating food or talking loudly on mobile phones (Moore, 2011). Patrol aimed at protecting the people and preserving the peace in the extent of accosting some anti-social behavior which tend to disturb the public peace. Beneficiaries of this research such as the business owners, the police itself and ordinary people wandering at the middle of the town of Bulusan will become aware and knowledgeable on how the police works in order to deny the opportunity to commit crime.

As in the case of the phenomenal growth of hip hop graffiti in the United States, a form of graffiti writing in Denver which ever increasing cases and identifying the factor in order to criminalize this kind of public disturbance by means of the effort of the police (Ferrell and Huidobro, 1993).At the peak period of crime prevention programs by the intensive patrols, the Bulusan Municipal Police Station (BMPS) saw its transition period to adopt the ever increasing efficiency of the international standard of making patrols and police visibilities to the said municipality, though a small rural area but under the threat of a petty insurgency which was arouse fear and disparity to the people of Bulusan.

Attitudes and other factors which affect the image and integrity of the police organization during the execution of strategies seem to be one of the precipitating factors on how the community join in with their participation in order to fight criminality, particularly in their areas. According to the study of Davis, R.C et al., 2005, the fall of citizens' complaints is because of the efforts of the commanders to promote respectful policing programs. It is depend on how the police forces argue and treat the people to seek a desired cooperation.

In the study of Patalinghug (2017), somewhere at Zamboanga Del Sur where it is revealed at the findings that the police are "much effective" in its anti-criminality campaign in the four (4) municipalities of the said province.

Since it was itself considered as the backbone of police organization, patrol plays a big role in crime prevention campaign not just to protect the properties, business establishments but also to preserve and maintain the harmony inside the entire jurisdiction. The importance of this study is to asses the good and bad side of the performance of the police inside the jurisdiction of the municipality of Bulusan in order to have a better understanding the essence preventing crime, and how the people treated with due respect and care during police operations. Kenny and Holmes (2020), identified the so called "penal populism" after the onset of war on drugs by President Rodrigo "Roa" Duterte, where there was an identified harsh punishment in relation to drug related cases. With this, the police negatively draws from the set of being a good example and the people started hating them. Asin the case of this study, the researcher aimed at identifying how the police perform their specific duties (patrol) in its anti-criminality campaign.

The study in **Predicting perceived police effectiveness in public housing: police contact, police trust, and police responsiveness** (Torres and J.A, 2017) pertains to the measurement of the effectiveness of the police somewhere at the United States where there is a rigid enforcement of curfew hours. Banishment is one of their tactics in enforcing punishment and those who violated the mandate shall suffer equivalent punishment. This is done through patrolling street-by-street in order to identify the suitability of the ordinance to maintain its impact to the feelings of the community.

Public housing authorities have implemented banishment policies giving police the authority to ban non-residents from public housing and arrest them for trespassing upon violating the ban. Scholars argue that banishment expands police powers because authorities need little reason to ban non-residents, are beyond judicial review, and can lead to racially disparate enforcement. However, it is unclear whether community policing may be able to mediate the negative effects of banishment, by building police trust, and still allow residents to perceive the police and banishment as effective (Torres, 2015).

In the study of Bayley and Garofalo (1989), they conclude that patrol should always be provided with skills and support from its peers and community. They argued that (1) violence, even verbal aggression, is relatively rare in police work; (2) most conflict is dampened by the arrival of the police, leaving little scope for the use of defusing tactics; and (3) the behavior of officers judged by colleagues to be skilled in minimizing violence is measurably different from the behavior of "average" patrol officers, and in ways that suggest that colleagues may be good judges of on-street performance.

What do we really know about police patrol? A systematic review of routine police patrol research (Dau, P.M, et. al., 2020). It was aimed at identifying the essence of police patrol especially in the study of Criminology. The scholars observed that there were no particular focus in terms of studying police patrol and its greater impact in crime prevention strategies; how the society protected and secured to their particular personal affairs and businesses. Research on routine police patrol has experienced little attention in criminology for the past four decades. Despite the fact that little is known about this mode of policing, a consensus seems to prevail regarding its ineffectiveness for crime deterrence and crime prevention. To emphasize this gap of research, this study systematically reviews existing literature on routine police patrol (Dau, Vandeviver, et al., 2020).

Tankebe (2008), argued in his findings that though perceptions of police effectiveness exercise a direct impact on perceived police trustworthiness, the relationship is stronger if the police are also perceived to be procedurally fair. The findings are significant as they show that building public trust in the police requires democratic reforms that simultaneously improve the capacity of the police to achieve both substantive effectiveness and procedural fairness.

The implementation of the Philippine National Police Anti-Criminality Program at Batasan Hills, Quezon City (Almoguerra, Buyo, et. al., 2019) aimed at identifying the effectiveness of the Quezon City police in terms of anti-criminality campaign to suppress and prevent the rampant proliferation of criminality with different mode of commissions, as in the case of studying the need to identify the effectiveness of the Bulusan Patrol Unit in their anti-criminality efforts to protect the citizenry. The type of crimes (blue collar and white collar) be the main concern of the crime prevention campaign to pursue the transparency (Rub and Jacob, 2014).

With the researcher's effort in determining capability of the Mobile Patrol Unit in the municipality of Bulusan, it is of great concern that there are certain beneficiaries that will benefit and will use of the positive output of this study. The following are the importance of this research to the identified beneficiaries:

Business Owners. Since this study focuses the anti-criminality campaign of the Bulusan Municipal Police Station particularly in conducting patrols, it has been observed that, despite the overall losses business sustain from crime and the impact that crime can have upon business turnover, crime against businesses has been subject to relatively little attention by academics and practitioners alike (Hibberd and Shapland 1993). With this, the researcher will be in a middle of effort just to radiate the findings of this research study in order for the business owners be benefitted.

Local Government Officials. To strengthen their campaign in their exclusive jurisdiction to preserve the welfare of the people and to exhibit great cooperation with the police by convincing people within their reach.

Tourists. Since Bulusan municipality is another spot for tourist attraction, this study will cover for the effectiveness of the patrol unit on how they offer escorts and certainty for the safety and welfare not only to the permanent residents but also to the transient individuals. Through this scholarly output, there will be a relative increase on the security and certainty on the part of the tourists after the police strengthened their campaign to deny the opportunity to commit crimes.

Municipal Police Station. As this study centered the objectives in determining their effectiveness, the output of this work will be beneficial to them to be able to assess their work whether it be effective or not, what are the needed programs to develop and the possible solutions to the problems they've encountered.

B. Objectives

To provide however the better result of this research work, the researcher identified different objectives namely:

- Determine the effectiveness of Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU) in the municipality of Bulusan as to their anti-criminality campaign.
- Identify their strategies in order to strengthen the program of crime prevention.
- Assess the perception of the people and the business-owners based on their experience as to the anti-criminality campaign of the MPU of the said municipality.
- Formulate management plan to enhance crime prevention program based on the findings.

II. THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

“To a large degree, the vision of crime prevention is a fully-pledged professional discipline is a grail for the future - but this is surely an irresistible challenge to practitioners, researchers, evaluators, and policy makers.” (Ekblom, 1996:87)

“**Situational Crime Prevention Theory**”, this theory best fits the researcher’s study as situational crime prevention is radically different from other forms of crime prevention as it seeks only to reduce opportunities for crime, not bring about lasting change in criminal or delinquent dispositions. Proceeding from an analysis of the circumstances giving rise to very specific kinds of crime and disorder, it introduces discrete managerial and environmental modifications to change the opportunity structure for those crimes to occur—not just the immediate physical and social settings in which the crimes occur, but also the wider societal arrangements that make the crimes possible (Clarke, 2018).

“**Police Omnipresence**”, high police visibility discourages criminals. Normally, criminals think twice before executing their plans if there is obvious presence of police officers. Thus, patrol activity should be carried in a manner that attracts maximum attention to the police officer or police vehicles. This theory applies the principle of overt operation or high police visibility (Pasco, 2010).

“**Low Profile Theory**”, low police visibility increases the opportunity to apprehend criminals. Deceptive absence of the police officer will let criminals believe that they will not be detected or caught if they execute crimes that they planned. In this theory, the objective is to attract as little attention as possible while on the process of patrolling. The officers should operate in a manner that it would be difficult for either criminals or the public to determine that police are around. The principle of covert operation is integrated in this theory (Pasco, 2010).

This study will be helpful to the police authorities to gain the perception of the community as to how they are effective in terms of preventing crime using routine patrols; since patrol was considered as the backbone of police organization, this plays a crucial role in preventing crime. It is known that random, routine patrol, conducted with no set objectives and a lack of sound planning, is not an efficient use of police resources and has little impact on deterring criminal activity (Hale, 1981). Therefore, it is imperative to have a study that measures their suitability in denying the opportunities to commit crime particularly in the Municipality of Bulusan.

In addition, this will create awareness on both police and community sector leading to safer place and well-aware people to the possible commission of crimes. A good cooperative efforts between police and community offers a great chance in order to remove the opportunities to commit crimes, and the police will always be in a high-morale due to some positive impact in as far as crime reduction is concern.

Fig. 1: Paradigm of the Study

III. DEFINITION OF TERMS

In this part, the researcher identified the different terms which will offer technicalities to the reader and may result to some vague and ambiguous interpretation, however the researcher makes it clear in this part.

Anti-Criminality Campaign. It refers to any operation which is conducted by the police for purpose of crime prevention and crime solution. It also involves tactical operation to emergency situation such as hostage crisis and violent mass rally (Pascual, 2019).

The anti-criminality campaign is used by this study in the determination of effectiveness of the MPU as to the conduct of routine patrols to the entire jurisdiction of the municipality of Bulusan.

Crime Prevention. Crime prevention involves any activity by an individual or group, public or private, which attempts to eliminate crime prior to it occurring or before any additional activity results (UNODC, 2019).

A common challenge when discussing 'crime prevention' is identifying exactly what is captured by the term. Defining crime prevention is difficult because, "[i]n practice, the term 'prevention' seems to be applied confusingly to a wide array of contradictory activities" (Brantingham and Faust, 1976, p. 284).

Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU). An urban emergency service system provides mobile units (vehicles) to respond to requests for service which can occur at any time and any place throughout a city (Chaiken and Larson, 1972)).

In relation to the researcher's study, MPU plays a vital role in denying the opportunity to commit crime and how does the people reacts and give comments as to their efficiency.

Routine Patrol. It is known that random, routine patrol, conducted with no set objectives and a lack of sound planning, is not an efficient use of police resources and has little impact on deterring criminal activity. Due to the fiscal limitations and resources and increasing public concerns about the escalation costs of government, it is more important than ever before that patrol operations be carefully planned, systematically conducted, and efficiently managed (Hale, 1981)

The experiment suggests that deployment strategies should be based on specific crime prevention and service goals, contrasted with routine preventive patrol (Kelling, Pate, et., al. 1974).

IV. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

- What are the strategies of the Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU) in its anti-criminality campaign in Bulusan Sorsogon?
- What are the experiences of business owners in Bulusan Sorsogon as to the anti-criminality campaign of the mobile patrol unit?

A. Design and Methodology

At this point, the researcher utilizes the different designs and methods on how the data gathered from the respective respondents as to the effectiveness of the MPU Bulusan in its anti-criminality campaign.

B. Research Design and Methodology

The researcher used Qualitative Research method. It is believed that Qualitative research is a process of naturalistic inquiry that seeks an in-depth understanding of social phenomena within their natural setting. It focuses on the "why" rather than the "what" of social phenomena and relies on the direct experiences of human beings as meaning-making agents in their every day lives (University of Texas). In qualitative research, the researcher is the instrument of data analysis. The researcher's ability to interpret the data

and to present the findings clearly makes a qualitative research study useful (Jacelon and O'Dell, 2005). It is also believes that qualitative research is a broad umbrella term that covers a wide range of techniques and philosophies; thus it is not easy to define (Hennink, Hutter, et. al., 2020).

For the fulfillment of the research objectives, the researcher is expected to gather data from the set of respondents through the use of Descriptive Method with the adoption of Survey approach in order to have a better result that is subject for interpretation and analysis. Using survey approach, it will define more the data as it serves as supplementary to interview conducted to specific sets of respondent. Survey are systems of collecting information from or about people to describe, compare or explain their knowledge, attitudes and behaviors (Fink, 2003).

Through this selected research design and methodology, data gathered from the respondents should be under evaluation to measure how it effective the MPU in their anti-criminality campaign in Bulusan, Sorsogon.

V. POPULATION AND LOCALE OF THE STUDY

In this part, the researcher choose the area of study and the specific set of respondents which will be the actors in order to gather data.

The study focused specifically in the Municipality of Bulusan, province of Sorsogon. Bulusan Municipality is a 4th class municipality in the province of Sorsogon, according to the 2020 census it has 23, 932 people. Being a 4th class municipality is quiet large for and challenging for police authorities in order to preserve peace and order. The mass of population is less dramatic in terms of its volume but it will not disqualify the integrity of this research because what matter is the existence of crime but not the amount or density of population at a given area. Bulusan municipality is a rural town loacted at the middle of the province of Sorsogon; hence, a town which previously under the threat of crimes particularly insurgency, it is so for the purpose as to determine the efficiency of the police to combat crimes in that particular area.

Fig. 2

The researcher believed that the data in the chosen respondents is better enough to have a better result for this research study as to their perception on the effectiveness of Mobile Patrol Unit of Bulusan PNP in its anti-criminality campaign. The data was expected to gather in the group of respondents particularly the business owners, selected groups in the PNP (Bulusan MPS) patrol unit, and selected groups in the community residing over the town (where there is a direct perception of the patrol units); they are the chosen respondents in this study as it believes that the effectiveness of the patrol unit lies upon the experience of the community as the main beneficiaries, but in some degree, the researcher choose selected PNP personnel to become fair.

VI. RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

	Frequency
1. Business Owners	10
2. PNP Patrol Units	10
Total	20

Table 1

The said respondents will subject into interviews (as well as survey) to gain their perceptions as to the effectiveness of MPU in its anti-criminality campaign. As to the exclusion, those persons who are not under the specific set respondents are expected to be not a participant of this research study; particularly those who are not a resident of the municipality of Bulusan. In the qualitative research, it is imperative to use a particular instrument just to correlate and examine the exact perception of the respondents as to the effectiveness of MPU, Bulusan MPS. Using interview guide will be best in order to get a desired result which is subject for the interpretation to have a clear picture as to what society perceives in terms of police efficiency, particularly patrol efficiencies.

A. Data Gathering Tools

In gathering of data, the researcher utilized the use of interview guide and administered to the set of respondents. This interview guide was previously furnished by the researcher anchored at the objectives of the study and identified problems. In the only reliability study to report agreement on individual items using a test-retest interview method, most of the items had only fair or poor agreement (Williams and J.B, 1988). The researcher adopted this method in order to have a better understanding as to the effectiveness of the MPU in their visibility operations.

Aside from the interview guide, the survey questionnaire was also utilized to supplement the gathering of data. The questionnaire consists of standardized questions that operationalize the measurement constructs. The goal is to present a uniform stimulus to respondents so that their responses are comparable (Martin, 2006).

B. Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher expected to gather the data by means of interview using electronic device to record for reference purposes. The interview should be focused on the research problem and anchored into the objectives of this study.

The researcher is expected to approach the said respondents asking for their permission and consent to gather for this research purposes. This will form part a sign of respect and courtesy for them to ensure the rapport during the interview.

In gathering data, the researcher will ensure that there should be no monetary reward or consideration just to permit the gathering of data. The respondents are advised to be free from any rewards or gifts in exchange for their accounts useful for this study.

The data was expected to gather at the exclusive jurisdiction of Bulusan municipality, and the respondents are selected carefully believing that they are enough to cover the needs (information) for this scholarly output.

The researcher may also gather for the data including crime rate and the most prevalent crime committed in the said municipality.

With this procedure, the data collected and provides a structured format that researchers and others can use to review the content and quality of papers, conduct systematic reviews, or develop manuscripts (Zaza, De Agüero, et., al. 2000).

C. Ethical Considerations

The researcher conducted study regarding the effectiveness of the MPU in their anti-criminality campaign without the use of any instrument or consideration for the advancement of the gathering of data that may result to bias and prejudice.

The data was gathered with full respect to the respondents seeking their consent for the interview and survey without however involving money or any monetary considerations.

Direct involvement and participation with people necessitates acknowledging the subjective nature and activity of the researcher as the “main tool” of research (Munhall, 1988). Through this literature, the researcher treated the respondents due respect not to create any embarrassing moment during interview and survey.

Data gathered from the set of respondents is treated with confidentiality and for research purposes only. This will not foster gap between the community and the police.

D. Presentation and Analysis

There were 20 statements out of the responses of twenty participants who answered the two sub-problems which enables the researcher to formulate the following emergent themes;

- What are the strategies of the Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU) in its anti-criminality campaign in Bulusan Sorsogon?
 - Increased Police Visibility
 - Positive Attitude
 - Multi-faceted Response
- What are the experiences of business owners in Bulusan Sorsogon as to the anti-criminality campaign of the mobile patrol unit?
 - Community Satisfaction
 - Good Police Performance
 - People and Business Security
 - Limited Patrol Areas

Police patrol deemed to be considered as the “backbone of police organization”; it comprises largest units making them more responsible to combat criminality and preserve peace and order within their area. Patrol units governed by a large scale of duties as the community depends on each other’s efforts just to preserve peace, and produce productive business efforts. The following are the vivid responses of the participants that will produce idea on the themes.

VII. ON STRATEGIES OF THE MOBILE PATROL UNIT (MPU) IN ITS ANTI-CRIMINALITY CAMPAIGN

Presented in this section are the three themes which emerged on the Strategies of the MPU. These are (a)Increased Police Visibility, (b)Positive Attitude and (c)Multi-Faceted Response.

Increased Police Visibility. People feel that they are secured if there is a heightened police visibility in the area. Referring to the anatomy of the crime, the only thing that police visibility can deny is the opportunity to commit crimes, hence this will cater huge part in preventing crimes. In the study of Johnson, M, et al. (2012), argued that the forest crime reduced when the police started to have a program that will directly address the illegal loggers. With this, we could see that police visibility plays a vital role not only to protect the general welfare of the public but also to preserve the welfare of the entire habitation.

The “psychology of omnipresence” is the theory which offers deterrence to the potential offender, providing them a fear of being caught before committing a crime. Winkel and Willem (1986) hypothesized three effects of increased police visibility; In the first place, a decreased fear of crime among the public is expected. Second, increased police visibility is hypothesized to result in lower estimates of subjective risks of victimization. Finally, it is predicted that police visibility will strengthen police-community relations. In addition, Quality of police visibility proved to be an important factor from the point of view of community policing, in which one of the main purposes is to improve

the relationship between the police and the public (Salmi, Voeten, et. al., 2001).

Similarly, the police will always look forward to always uphold the essence of their presence and the purpose of this in preventing crime. MPU of Bulusan MPS seem to be more aggressive to secure the people in their area including the degree of security to different business establishments. “There’s no need to relax”, one of the response by the PNP participant during interview amid of very low crime rate as they believe that crime will always exists even in front of police officers. In relation to the study of Salmi and Groonros, et al (2004), their findings indicate that a simple act for the police, such as stepping out of the car every now and then, i.e. not only in crime-related situations, has a positive impact on the fear of crime as expressed by the public. Therefore, police visibility tactics will always endeavors a broad aid in crime prevention strategies.

Positive Attitude. This kind of personality trait will be the other side of the weapon the police must possess, it is some for the few police officers assigned in their beats having this kind of personality. People sometimes experienced arrogant officers in the street making them reluctant to cooperate when the police seek their help, hence, one of the participant revealed that doing police visibility must be coupled with “positive attitude” towards the people. No single police program can produce positive attitude towards police, because attitudes toward the police are firmly embedded in the social structure (Decker, 1981). With this, police must embed greater programs in order to have a good image and positive result as far as perception of the community to their attitudes is concern.

Aside from the reduction of crime, Bulusan Municipal Police Station experienced a low count of reported incidents, and they believed that the only reason for this is the effort of this office to secure the municipality and remove the opportunity to commit crime through the help of police visibility and good community relation. Moreover, the agency should have officers who respect individual rights, should address crime and order problems by using all available community resources, and should cooperate and coordinate with neighboring law enforcement agencies. Communication between the agency and the public should be open, and a positive attitude toward the media is essential (Couper, 1983).

It is observed that people had their own instinct which is already negative if they saw a uniformed personnel, it is the uniform that makes them aloof that precipitates the negative perception. The citizen's attitude is negatively affected by the traditional military style police uniform in conjunction with the authoritarian attitude exhibited by police officers in performance of their duties (Bell, 1982); but it is itself the police assigned in their beats to save their image by displaying positive attitude towards citizens. Participants also revealed that it is the best way in order to seek for the cooperative effort of the people, and to aid the PCR division to win the cooperation of the community. In relation to the study of Albrecht and Green (1977), they

proposed that the effectiveness of such programs is hindered by their failure to consider that public attitudes toward the police do not exist in isolation, but are a part of a broader complex of attitudes toward the system of legal justice and its various representatives. Therefore, positive attitude will cover all negative side and will seek for the people to be comfortable with the patrol units.

Multi-Faceted Response. In as far as the police service is concern, they have a lot of responsibilities up to the moment that even the minute effort that an ordinary person can do will also part of their functions. Based on the data gathered from the participants, they argued that the MPU of Bulusan MPS do their necessary job to promote positive impact to the community and to serve them with all their efforts. Multiple programs will also secure multiple responses. Percy (1980) argued in his study that response time and citizen perceptions of response time are factors which police agencies can directly influence as they attempt to provide more satisfactory services to citizens.

This multi various responses make people aware about the presence and programs of the police agency in their specific locality. As there is different area of topography and cultures, there are also different approach and programs that is observed in order to cater and overcome the needs of the people to protect them from any criminal activities. Therefore, perception and positive feedback is one of the main concern. Research on citizens' perceptions of the police has previously found that citizen demographics, contact with police, and neighborhood context influence perceptions(Wentz andSchlimjen, 2011).

In the study conducted by Sung (2006), it is observed that Undemocratic countries and the advanced democracies experienced the highest levels of police effectiveness, whereas middle-range countries showed lower ratings of police performance. However, based on the data gathered from the participants, it is not a big deal how it is advance the police has. It is about more on efforts and strategies which always touch the satisfaction level of the people. Therefore, Police should implement a process-based model of service that emphasizes citizens' feelings of neighborhood safety and police response as important predictors of positive evaluations of service(Dukes, Portillos et. al 2009).

VIII. ON THE EXPERIENCES OF BUSINESS OWNERS IN BULUSAN SORSOGON AS TO THE ANTI-CRIMINALITY CAMPAIGN OF THE MOBILE PATROL UNIT

Another presentation from the participants which ended into the formulation of four themes as to the experiences of business owners in anti-criminality campaign of the MPU. These themes are (a)Community Satisfaction, (b)Good Police Performance, (c)People and Business Security, and (d)Limited Patrol Areas.

Community Satisfaction. One concept of policing directly asserts that police is the servant of the people and their yardstick of efficiency was depend on the absence of crime (Modern Concept and Home Rule Theory). The degree of satisfaction is another concern of good policing

system, as it is one of the main targets of the said method. As part of this study, the researcher balances the equation of data from the respondents just to determine their perceptions and degree of satisfaction, it seems that the business owners express their satisfaction in adherence to the police service (specifically patrol units)in Bulusan. It is unhelpful and unrealistic to demand perfect police; instead we should aim to achieve 'good enough' policing, re-evaluating and questioning the concepts of fairness and effectiveness (Bowling, 2007).

The notion that community residents are key players responsible for the well-being of the larger society has become a cornerstone of approaches to modern policing in democratic societies. That is, residents partner with police to help maintain social order (Nalla, Mesko, et al., 2016). This is where community satisfaction resides and will dependent on the police effectiveness. Study recognizes that law enforcement is faced with the need to develop line officers who are capable of not only enforcing the law but also of participating in the resolution of social problems associated with crime (Coffey, Eldefonso, et al., 1971).

Moreover, the service should always be in a transparent way in order to build a strong tie between police and the community. Albrecht and Green (1977) proposed in their study that the effectiveness of such programs is hindered by their failure to consider that public attitudes toward the police do not exist in isolation, but are a part of a broader complex of attitudes toward the system of legal justice and its various representatives.

Good police Performance. In as far as the service and effectiveness of the police service is concern, it is imperative to look for the community satisfaction. As concerned in this study, the effectiveness of the MPU in its anti-criminality campaign rests on the effort of their team to uphold the maintenance of order in the locality. No role is more important than that of patrol officers, who are entrusted with the responsibility and authority to provide critical quality services to citizens. Role changes for officers are reflected in new training efforts that communicate the role expectations, and supported by new performance evaluation processes that reinforce these expectations (Oettmeier and Wycoff, 1977). In addition, trainings and consistency to the programs will always bring satisfaction to the people and this satisfaction will be better to label them as a good public servants.

Pugh (1986) described in his study the qualities essential for good police performance. These include common sense, mature judgment, and the ability to react quickly and effectively to problem situations. Moreover, police do need to upgrade their personal trainings and capabilities in order to fully equipped with the existing programs in anti-criminality; just to ensure that the public is fully aware and they feel that the police are doing the same part as what expected.

People and Business Security. Security is always be the main concern of a good policing. That is why police officers need to conduct patrols without considering the exact time and terrain conditions. The greater the effort of the police to prevent crime is also the bigger of investments

by the business owners which offers opportunity occupation to the jobless sectors.

The community policing effort was seen as a means to make a transformational change to become a learning organization with the goal of improving the delivery of police services (Ford, 2007). So the work between police and the community is a good idea on how to ensure that the crime is always prevented. There are numerous critics, setbacks, stigma and other negative feedback which always come into reality that police sometimes are guilty of some misconduct which offers also negativity on the eyes of the community. This will form part as an evaluation process on how to improve the next time service to the people, seeking their cooperation and winning their satisfaction to the police services.

Results thus suggest that positive styles of policing will significantly affect police-community relations, and that police-community relations programs stressing officer-citizen interaction in a law enforcement context will have the highest probability of success (Scaglione and Condon, 1980). The success will all be beneficial to us, not just the business owners but also the general public. Therefore, it is a positive indication that the police are doing their just effort to monitor the surroundings and restore order within the locality; winning the public cooperation is the foundation of a good policing, and having a good flow of policing will offer better protection to the community and to the business establishments. However, there are some instances that the concept of policing is under compromised, in the instance when the police had closeness to community and politicians leading to corruptions, especially in inner cities, where police have been charged with enforcing laws that had been enacted by conservative rural-dominated legislatures, but that found little support in a hurly-burly of urban life (Fyfe, 1993).

Limited Patrol Areas. Participants honestly secured a data that will uncover the fact that the police in Bulusan had their own limited areas in as far as patrolling is concern. Fu (1990), outlined in his study the creation of China's "modern" police force as they criticized community policing because it is seem to be static and outmoded. It is also argued in his study that in order to meet the economic reform and modernization in the cities, police should put on their uniform and conduct regular patrol on the streets, so that they can make quick responses. In relation to the study of Fu, the business-owners in Bulusan revealed their wish to the police to perform routine patrols to the distant areas not covered by the center of the town. Though very little experience having been victimized by criminals in as far as the business is concern, but they are also seeking for police presence in the respective barangays.

Answering assigned calls and conducting general surveillance by patrolling are the two most time consuming sorts of patrol activity. There is great variation in the amount of time officers on patrol spend answering assigned calls (Whitaker, 1981).

IX. CORROBORATION

Hale (1981), argued in his study that thoughtful planning and direction of patrol activities is still uncommon in most police agencies. It is known that random, routine patrol, conducted with no set objectives and a lack of sound planning, is not an efficient use of police resources and has little impact on deterring criminal activity. Therefore, they need to take necessary efforts in order to have an efficiency the program they intend to utilize to prevent crime.

Miller (1995) examines the techniques and capabilities of the Patrol Units in terms of procedures for dealing with substance abuse and gangs, field interviews, arrest procedures, police investigations and reports, courtroom procedures, handling civil disturbances and other disasters, police officer survival, and the future of law enforcement. The effectiveness of the MPU rests solely to the resources of their department, including the knowledge, capabilities, experience and trainings of different patrol officers for the fulfillment of the efficient and productive crime prevention programs.

Kolesar and Walker (1975), conducted a simulation procedures on how the police responded immediately to the reported incidents. They used simulation procedures on how to quickly drop the patrol beat and change it into another direction with proper delegation to fellow officers. With regards to the effectiveness of the patrol units, study revealed that the simulation procedures is one of the effective measures in order to strengthen the programs of crime prevention.

Goss, Bramer et al., (2008), studies the effect of intensive patrol to highways in order to reduce the prevalence of fatal vehicular accidents. This relates to the current topic where there is an assessment procedure on how the society responded to the questions as to how and what are the factors that make the patrol units more effective.

Bohmfalk (1998), determine the significance in the use of bicycle patrols is a key element in many community policing programs. They are used in drug enforcement operations, malls, tourist assistance, campus patrol, business districts, neighborhoods, and special operations. We all know the positive side of the bicycle patrol compared to the other types of patrolling methods. It can develop stealth and element of surprise to the potential commission of crime. Further, it will also provide a positive impact to the community as the police who used bicycle for patrol was seen to be rare in present day.

Maxson, Hennigan et al., (2003) revealed that Police can improve public opinion by increasing their informal contacts with citizens. Police can increase residents' approval of their job performance by participating in community meetings, increasing officers' visibility in neighborhoods, and talking with citizens. These informal contacts had a positive impact on job approval ratings even when other factors associated with lower approval ratings--such as residents' perceptions that their neighborhoods were crime ridden, dangerous, and disorderly--were present. Informal contacts with police also lessened the negative

impact of residents’ formal contacts with police, such as being arrested or questioned by police.

Cawathe (2007) used model a road network using an edge-weighted graph in which edges represent streets, vertices represent intersections, and weights represent importance of the corresponding streets. He describe efficient methods that use this input to determine the most important patrol routes. This correlates with the impact of the police patrol services which will be the future basis of the people whether they do an effective crime prevention programs or not.

X. FINDINGS

Based from the data gathered from the respondents, it is observed that the Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU) in the municipality of Bulusan is effective in implementing programs related to the anti-criminality campaign. But some respondents argued that the said patrol units is exclusively within the entire town without however reaching the far distant barangays. Some of them also inferred that extension of the patrol scope should be observed.

XI. CONCLUSIONS

- The business-owners in the municipality of Bulusan has a good experience and agreed to the effective response of the MPU.
- There is a limited patrol scope without reaching the far distant Barangays.

XII. RECOMMENDATIONS

At some point, based on the findings of the study the researcher come up with the formulation of the recommendations which may be more advantageous to the MPU of Bulusan MPS.

- They should conduct more trainings and seminars to the business owners on how they will fully protect their businesses.
- The police (MPU), business owners and the general public must need to take a one-tied cooperation to fully implement the anti-criminality campaign.
- The MPU should exceed their area of responsibility in conducting patrols, especially in a far distant Barangays

PROGRAMS	ACTIVITY	PERSONS INVOLVE
1. Intensive Patrol	- Conduct patrol in the distant barangays outside the población of its municipality. - The patrolling in the distant brgy should be atleast two (2)-times-a-day.	- Mobile Patrol Unit (MPU)
2. Enhanced Community Relation	- Reach out the business-owners and the people even outside the scope of patrol. - Dialogue regularly with brgy captains particularly officials in far distant places of Bulusan.	- MPU and its COP/OIC

Table 1: Proposed Management Plan

• Author Contributions

J. Guelas – He conducted alone all the efforts in order to possibly finish and give emphasis on what was the desired result of this research study.

• Competing Interests

This paper is for academic purposes only. This will not cover any unduly disadvantages that can put any situation into peril.

• Grant Information

The author is a scholar in PhD by the Commission on Higher Education. All the desired expenses will fully covered by the said commission including that of the publications that will previously performed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To my Wife (Lyn FurioGeraban-Guelas) for putting additional insight to boost my personality to finish this scholarly output.

To my colleague, who have done so much advises and assistance to enlighten me in a vague differences of conducting research study.

To our professor, Doctor Robino D. Cawi for putting us lots of information on how this study become possible.

To God be the Glory!

REFERENCES

[1.] Almoguerra, J., Buyo, R., Hernandez, D., Impil, R., Templonuevo, R., & Cuntapay, M. S. (2019). The Implementation of the Philippine National Police Anti-Criminality Program at Batasan Hills in Quezon City. Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 1(1).

[2.] Albrecht, S. L., & Green, M. (1977). Attitudes toward the police and the larger attitude complex: implications for police-community relationships. *Criminology*, 15(1), 67-86.

[3.] Bayley, D. H., & Garofalo, J. (1989). The management of violence by police patrol officers. *Criminology*, 27(1), 1-26.

[4.] Bell, D. J. (1982). Police uniforms, attitudes, and citizens. *Journal of criminal justice*, 10(1), 45-55.

[5.] Bowling, B. (2007). Fair and effective policing methods: Towards ‘good enough’policing. *Journal of Scandinavian studies in criminology and crime prevention*, 8(S1), 17-32.

[6.] Brantingham, P. J., & Faust, F. L. (1976). A conceptual model of crime prevention. *Crime & Delinquency*, 22(3), 284-296.

- [7.] Chaiken, J. M., & Larson, R. C. (1972). Methods for allocating urban emergency units: a survey. *Management Science*, 19(4-part-2), P110-P130.
- [8.] Clarke, R. The Theory and Practice of Situational Crime Prevention. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology*.
- [9.] Couper, D. C. (1983). How to rate your local police. Washington, DC: Police Executive Research Forum.
- [10.] Dau, P. M., Vandeviver, C., Dewinter, M., Witlox, F., & Vander Beken, T. (2020). WHAT DO WE REALLY KNOW ABOUT POLICE PATROL?: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF ROUTINE POLICE PATROL RESEARCH.
- [11.] Decker, S. H. (1981). Citizen attitudes toward the police: A review of past findings and suggestions for future policy. *Journal of police science and administration*, 9(1), 80-87.
- [12.] Dukes, R. L., Portillos, E., & Miles, M. (2009). Models of satisfaction with police service. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*.
- [13.] Ferrell, J., & Stewart-Huidobro, E. (2021). *Crimes of style: Urban graffiti and the politics of criminality*. Routledge.
- [14.] Fink, A. (2003). *How to design survey studies*. Sage.
- [15.] Hale, C. D., & Chapman, S. G. (1981). *Police patrol, operations and management*. NJ: Wiley.
- [16.] Hennink, M., Hutter, I., & Bailey, A. (2020). *Qualitative research methods*. Sage.
- [17.] Hibberd, M., & Shapland, J. (1993). *Violent crime in small shops*. London: Police Foundation.
- [18.] Hughes, G. (1998). *Understanding crime prevention*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- [19.] Jacelon, C. S., & O'Dell, K. K. (2005). Analyzing qualitative data. *Urologic Nursing*, 25(3), 217-220.
- [20.] Johnson, M., Fang, F., & Tambe, M. (2012). Patrol strategies to maximize pristine forest area. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (Vol. 26, No. 1, pp. 295-301)*.
- [21.] Kenny, P. D., & Holmes, R. (2020). A new penal populism? Rodrigo Duterte, public opinion, and the war on drugs in the Philippines. *Journal of East Asian Studies*, 20(2), 187-205.
- [22.] Martin, E. (2006). Survey questionnaire construction. *Survey methodology*, 13.
- [23.] Moore, S. (2011). Understanding and managing anti-social behaviour on public transport through value change: The considerate travel campaign. *Transport Policy*, 18(1), 53-59.
- [24.] Munhall, P. L. (1988). Ethical considerations in qualitative research. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 10(2), 150-162.
- [25.] Nalla, M. K., Meško, G., & Modic, M. (2018). Assessing police–community relationships: is there a gap in perceptions between police officers and residents?. *Policing and society*, 28(3), 271-290.
- [26.] Pascual Jr., (2019). Implementation of Anti-Criminality Program of the Philippine National Police in the City of Antipolo.
- [27.] Patalinghug, M. (2017). Implemented Crime Prevention Strategies of PNP in Salug Valley, Zamboanga Del Sur, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(3).
- [28.] Percy, S. L. (1980). Response time and citizen evaluation of police. *Journal of Police Science and Administration*, 8(1), 75-86.
- [29.] Rub, J. (2014). From habitually to awareness: tools for dealing with an increase in “preventive awareness” of white-collar criminality by media campaign.
- [30.] Salmi, S., Voeten, M. J., & Keskinen, E. (2000). Relation between police image and police visibility. *Journal of community & applied social psychology*, 10(6), 433-447.
- [31.] Salmi, S., Grönroos, M., & Keskinen, E. (2004). The role of police visibility in fear of crime in Finland. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*.
- [32.] Sung, H. E. (2006). Police effectiveness and democracy: shape and direction of the relationship. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*.
- [33.] Tankebe, J. (2008). Police effectiveness and police trustworthiness in Ghana: An empirical appraisal. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 8(2), 185-202.
- [34.] Torres, J. A. (2017). Predicting perceived police effectiveness in public housing: Police contact, police trust, and police responsiveness. *Policing and society*, 27(4), 439-459.
- [35.] Wentz, E. A., & Schlimgen, K. A. (2012). Citizens' perceptions of police service and police response to community concerns. *Journal of Crime and Justice*, 35(1), 114-133.
- [36.] Williams, J. B. (1988). A structured interview guide for the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 45(8), 742-747.
- [37.] Winkel, F. W. (1986). Reducing fear of crime through police visibility: A field experiment. *Criminal Justice Policy Review*, 1(4), 381-398.
- [38.] Zaza, S., Wright-De Agüero, L. K., Briss, P. A., Truman, B. I., Hopkins, D. P., Hennessy, M. H., ... & Task Force on Community Preventive Services. (2000). Data collection instrument and procedure for systematic reviews in the Guide to Community Preventive Services. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 18(1), 44-74.

Author: Jaynor G. Guelas
Research Scholar Department of Criminal Justice Education, University of the Cordilleras, Philippines
Estenias Science Foundation School, Casiguran, Sorsogon
Corresponding author: Jaynor G. Guelas
Email: jaynorguelas21@gmail.com

Author Information

Name	:	Jaynor G. Guelas
Designation	:	Student
Department	:	Criminal Justice Education
University	:	Estenias Science Foundation School
Mail ID	:	jaynorguelas21@gmail.com
Contact No.	:	09070332227
Course	:	Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice
Address	:	San Rafael, Bulusan, Sorsogon, Philippines
ORCID ID	:	0000-0002-9165-4426

Jaynor Gerolia Guelas previously obtained his Bachelor of Science in Criminology at Veritas College of Irosin Sorsogon (Philippines). He passed the board examination on December 2017 and became a full-time faculty at the said institution for two (2) years. He is also a graduate of Master of Science in Criminal Justice (MSCJ) in Bicol college. Now, he is enrolled at the University of the Cordilleras taking up a degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice with Specialization in Criminology. Presently he is a scholar of the Commission on Higher Education Institution (CHED) Region V and a review lecturer at the different review centers and criminology schools teaching major subjects in Criminal Justice.